

Effect of Cassava Waste Water Effluent on Growth of *Zea Mays* (Maize) Seedlings

Okonkwo, N.N.¹, Orji, M.U.¹, Umeoduagu, N.D.², Nwiyi, I.U.¹, Awari, V.G.²,
Victor-Ebo, P.U.², Orji, C.C.¹ and Ofunwa, J.O.²,

¹Department of Applied Microbiology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, PMB 5025, Awka, Nigeria.

²Department of Microbiology, Tansian University, Umunya, Anambra, Nigeria

³Department of Science Laboratory Technology, Delta State University of Science and Technology, PMB 05, Ozoro, Delta State, Nigeria

⁴Department of Food Science and Technology, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, PMB 5025, Awka, Nigeria.

Corresponding Author Email: us.ogbonna@unizik.edu.ng

Abstract

Nigeria, the world's largest producer of cassava, very unfortunately, has consistently generated so much waste from cassava mills which are usually discharged on land or water indiscriminately and this in turn, affects the biota, as well as resulting in environmental pollution, which can also inhibits the growth of vegetations and thus, reduces the entire fertility of the soil. This study was aimed at analyzing the effect of cassava processing effluent on seedling height, biomass, chlorophyll and protein content of maize (*Zea mays*) plants. The physiochemical properties of cassava wastewater showed that it contained some heavy metals and highly acidic. The inhibitory effect of cassava effluent on the germination and growth of *Zea mays* was shown, whereby the height, biomass, chlorophyll and protein content were 7cm, 7.81, 6.4 and 1.34 compared to the control that were 15cm, 11.55, 7.93 and 2.46 respectively. The study clearly concluded that cassava effluent is toxic and is detrimental to crop and food-production economy. Further development of microbial processes that is efficient in extreme environmental conditions and contaminant toxicity, is required to reduce cyanide and other heavy metal pollution. Thus, this biological method, which is efficient, cost-effective and environmentally acceptable, is desired to degrade cyanide and other heavy metal pollution.

Keywords: Cassava wastewater, Effluent, *Zea mays*, Seedlings

1. Introduction

The genus *Manihot* incorporates over 200 species of which *Manihotesculent crantz* is the most important, from the nutritional and economic point of view commonly known as cassava, manioc, tapioca and yucca cassava (*Manihotesculenta Crantz*) is a root tuber crop that is widely

cultivated in the tropical regions of the world (Agu *et al.*, 2014; Okigbo *et al.*, 2015; Agu *et al.*, 2023). It is mainly a food crop whose tubers are harvested between 7-13 months, the tubers are quite rich in carbohydrate (85.9%) with very small amount of protein (1.3%) in addition to cyanogenic glucoside (Agu *et al.*, 2016; Okonkwo *et al.*, 2023). This high carbohydrate content makes cassava a major food item especially for the low income earners in most tropical countries especially Africa and Asia (Desse and Taye 2016). Cassava is believed to have originated from south America to other Northern America, cassava was introduced in the 16th century around Congo river basins. In sub Sahara Africa, cassava is a major stable food that is consumed in processed forms in many areas. In West Africa and Nigeria in a particular the crop is mostly consumed as garri, a dry granulated meal made from fermented cassava. Currently, Nigeria is the highest producer of cassava in the world with growth and processing of more cassava for domestic and international needs.

Traditional garri production is associated with discharged of large amount of water, hydrocyanic acid and organic matter in the form of peels and sieves from the pulp as waste products. Around cassava mill, the liquid waste is indiscriminately discharged and allowed to accumulate, producing offensive odors and unsightly scenarios. The high cyanide content from the effluent equally possesses significant threat to humans and the environment, which calls for regulations in the discharge of the waste generated. The effluents when incorporated into the soil exert effects on the soil itself. When discharged, it is acted upon by soil microorganisms, releasing gases into the soil which other breakdown products are trapped in the soil.

The increased utilization of processed cassava products has increased the environmental pollution associated with the disposal of effluents. The highly offensive odour emanating from the fermenting effluent calls for regulation in the discharge of waste generated. In most areas, cassava mills are mainly on small scale basis, owned and managed by individuals who have no basic knowledge of environmental protection. Though on small scale basis, there are many of them, which when put together, create enormous impact on the environment. Cassava also contains much pollutant such as disease-causing pathogens e.g. bacteria and fungi, (Igbiosa, and Igiehon, 2015). Disposal of agricultural by-products such as cassava waste from processing activities is a concern in Nigeria. Pollution-induced changes in microbial communities can lead to the loss of ecosystem services such as soil fertility, water purification, and carbon sequestration. Disruption of soil microbial communities, for example, can reduce soil fertility and productivity, compromising agricultural yields and ecosystem resilience. Similarly, contamination of aquatic ecosystems by cassava

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effluents can impair water quality and disrupt aquatic microbial communities responsible for nutrient cycling and purification (Jansson *et al.*, 2020). Bioremediation helps solve this problem of pollution (Agu *et al.*, 2015, Anaukwu *et al.*, 2016; Okafor *et al.*, 2016).

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 MAIZE GROWTH EXPERIMENTATION

2.1.1 Seed sample collection and viability test

Zea mays commonly known as maize seeds were collected from Eke-Awka market in Awka City of Anambra State. The seeds were sorted, cleaned and tested for viability using the method of Idu and Olorunfeni (1998). The seeds were put in bowls of water and left for 5 minutes. Submerged seeds were collected and used while the seeds that remained afloat were discarded. The fresh cassava processing effluent was collected from Amansea village, Awka-North local government Area of Anambra State.

2.1.2 Soil sample preparation and growth studies

Two sets of experimental poly-pots were used for the growth experiments following modified methods of Karunyai *et al.* (1994). Poly-pots of 20cm diameter were filled with garden soils that contained farmyard manure collected from Amansea farms. A set were irrigated with the effluent-water mix at concentrations of 25, 50, 75 and 100% (v/v) effluent everyday for 15 days while control soils were irrigated with 1 L of deionized water. Soil samples from three replicates were air-dried at 80°C for elemental analysis.

Another set of Poly-pots were filled with garden soil that contained farmyard manure. Five seeds of *Zea mays*, were sown in the pots each and watered everyday for 28 days to allow for habituation of the seedlings prior to experimental treatment. The 28 days-old healthy seedlings were irrigated with the effluent-water mix at concentrations of 25,50,75 and 100% everyday for 15 days, with one serving as the control where the plants were irrigated with water only. The same quantity of effluent-water mix and water were used for irrigation treatment and control plants respectively. Plant samples were taken and analyzed for different parameters thereafter.

2.1.3 Method of data collection/analysis

Heights of plants were measured using a tape and number of leaves were counted and recorded. Heights of Plants and their number of leaves samples from three replicates were measured.

2.1.4 Element Analysis of the Soil and Plant Samples

The oven-dried plant materials samples (stem, leaf and root) at 80°C and soils were digested and filtered following the methods of Karunyal *et al.* (1994). The concentrations of Mg, Ca, K, Zn, Na, Cd, Cn, Cu and Pb were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry.

2.1.5 Total Chlorophyll Determination

Total chlorophyll was estimated using the method of Arnon (1949). Samples one gram each were weighed and after grinding the material with pestle and mortar, the chlorophylls in each sample were extracted with a mixture of acetone and ethyl alcohol (4:1) by repeatedly homogenizing in a blender. Supernatant solution containing chlorophylls was decanted with extracting solution. For using Zscheile and Comar's coefficients, this extract was transferred to ethyl ether. Absorbance of these solutions were recorded at 645, 652, 663, 665 and 630nm wavelengths and concentration of chlorophyll a, b and total was determined. Correlation was worked out between 645nm and 663 nm and also between 645nm and 652nm. Arnon formula was calculated as under:

Chlorophyll a g/g fresh weight sample = OD at 645 x 0.02969

Chlorophyll b g/g fresh weight sample = OD at 645 x 0.01096

Total Chlorophyll g/g fresh weight sample = OD at 645 x 0.04347

Total Chlorophyll b (mg/ml) x final volume (mL)

2.1.6 Method of Protein Determination

Protein was determined according to the method of Lowry *et al.* (1951). To 1ml of the test solution, 5ml of solution D (copper reagent) was mixed thoroughly by vortexing and standing at room temperature for 10min. 0.5ml of solution E (Folin- Ciocalteu reagent), was mixed rapidly and incubated for 30mins at room temperature. The absorbance at 600nm against reagent blank not containing protein was measured. The concentration was estimated by referring to a standard curve obtained at the same time using known concentrate of bovine serum

2.1.7 Statistical Analysis

Data were presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) of three replicates. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to test significance of variations within and among the groups. When significant difference was indicated by ANOVA, Tukey test was used for statistical analysis to make pair-wise comparisons between means. A statistical package for social sciences (SPSS) software was used for statistical analysis in this study and test for significance between means was implied at P = 0.05 level.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Element analysis of garden soil treated with cassava effluent at various concentrations

The physiochemical properties of the garden soil flooded with cassava waste water effluent at different concentrations shows that it is highly acidic (Table 1). As the concentration of the cassava mill effluent increases, there are also an increase in the values of the heavy metals. This can lead to pollution that will effect soil fertility and also cause health hazard and problems to the environment (Sanchez *et al.*, 1999). This resulted in the inhibition of plant growth and germination, as in *Zea mays* seeds treated with 25-100% of cassava waste water (Olorunfemi *et al.*, 2007).

The seeds of *Zea mays* germinated only in the soil treated with 25% effluent, but the one planted in the 50, 75 and 100% cassava waste water effluent soils did not germinate and no growth was observed. This is because of the high acidity of the effluents, which rise as the concentration rises. For the soil treated with cassava effluent for 15days before planting, the germination of seeds of *Zea mays* on 25% cassava effluent was inhibited until the seventeenth day of experimental period before they start germinating. The delay may be because of the acidity of the soil before planting as was reported by Olorunfemi *et al.*, 2007. Then that of 50%, 75% and 100% did not show any growth.

Table pH of garden soil pretreated with cassava effluent at different concentrations

1:

Treatment	0	25	50	75	100
pH	6.35	4.97	4.42	4.21	4.15

Table 2: Element analysis of garden soil treated with cassava effluent at various concentrations

Treatm ent	Mg	Ca	K	Cn	Zn	Na	Cd	Cu	Pb
0	4.95±0 .23	4.84±0 .02	2.13±0 .05	0.05±0 .03	2.65±0 .02	1.65±0 .13	1.45±0 .02	0.000±0 .00	0.00±0 .00
25	5.31±0 .14	5.02±0 .06	2.74±0 .34	1.62±0 .12	3.42±0 .03	1.92±0 .13	1.66±0 .03	0.05±0. 23	0.02±0 .15
50	5.37±0 .08	5.15±0 .12	3.62±0 .07	3.02±0 .04	3.72±0 .05	2.11±0 .04	1.86±0 .16	0.09±0. 12	0.04±0 .03
75	5.83±0 .11	5.67±0 .03	3.85±0 .02	4.13±0 .08	3.80±0 .24	2.23±0 .03	1.97±0 .07	0.17±0. 33	0.12±0 .04
100	5.92±0 .04	5.75±0 .05	4.96±0 .33	4.25±0 .12	3.87±0 .33	2.55±0 .14	2.42±0 .03	0.24±0. 03	0.14±0 .22

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Mean values of 3 replicates after 15 days of adding cassava effluent. Concentrations (mg g⁻¹ dry weight)

3.2 Effect of cassava effluent on plant height, number of leaves and biomass of *Zea mays*.

Throughout the experimental period, the seedlings of *Zea mays* irrigated with water grew very well, and their heights were significantly higher than seedlings irrigated with the effluent. The number of leaves they have is more than that of seedlings irrigated with the effluent (Table 3). Growth of the seedlings irrigated with the cassava effluents was inhibited after which they started withering. Except for the plants irrigated with 25% cassava effluent which were used for the analysis, those irrigated with 50, 75 and 100% did not show considerable increase in the number of leaves produced compared to control plants. Coleoptiles of *Zea mays*, in controls soils emerged above soil level four days after planting and the seedlings grew well. In *Zea mays* the mean height attained on 25% cassava effluent treated soils was 7cm compared to seedlings on control soils which attained 15cm height and this was also apparent in the differences in the number of leaves produced by each set of the plants. The inhibitory effect of cassava effluent on the germination and growth of the *Zea mays*, corresponds with the results obtained for the inhibitory effect on germination of the same cereal as reported in an earlier experiment (Olorunfemi *et al.*, 2007).

Table 3: Effect of cassava effluent on plant height, number of leaves and biomass of *Zea mays*.

Analysis	Control	25(%)	50(%)	75(%)	100(%)
Plant Height(cm)	15	7	0	0	0
Number of leaves	10	6	0	0	0
Biomass (g plant ⁻¹)	11.55	7.81	0	0	0

Mean values of 3 replicates after 15 days of adding cassava effluent

0 = Withering

Table 4: Effect of cassava effluent on protein content of *Zea mays*

Analysis	Control	25(%)	50(%)	75(%)	100(%)
Protein %	2.46	1.34	0	0	0

0 = Withering

Table 6: Effect of cassava effluent on chlorophyll content of *Zea mays*

Analysis	Control	25(%)	50(%)	75(%)	100(%)
Chlorophyll (mg)	7.93	6.4	0	0	0

0 = Withering

4.0 Conclusions

The occurrence of heavy metals in soils may be beneficial or toxic to the environment. Excess of metals may produce some common effect of individual metals on different plants. The biota may require some of these elements in trace quantities but at higher concentrations there may be toxicity problems. The presence of some heavy metals in the cassava effluent in this study may as well partly account for the inhibition of germination and growth of the *Zea Mays* and there is need to remediate this effluent to avoid pollution.

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